

1 **Predictive Modeling and Spatial Distribution of Pancreatic Cancer in Africa Using**
2 **Machine Learning-Based Spatial Model.**

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14
15 **Abstract**

16
17 **Background:** Pancreatic cancer (PC) is a highly invasive malignancy with a poor prognosis,
18 particularly in advanced stages, contributing significantly to global cancer-related mortality.
19 While incidence rates are rising globally, with particular concern in developing regions such as
20 Africa, early detection remains a major challenge due to the lack of reliable predictive tools.
21 Machine learning (ML) techniques, particularly in combination with spatial and temporal
22 analysis, offer promising potential in improving the early prediction and risk stratification of
23 PC, particularly in underserved populations. **Methods:** This study utilizes data extracted from
24 the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) 2021 estimates, which provides comprehensive health
25 metrics, including incidence, prevalence, and mortality rates for PC across 204 countries. The
26 study applied three machine learning algorithms: Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient
27 Boosting (XGBoost), and Support Vector Regression (SVR) to predict PC outcomes based on
28 demographic and temporal predictors. Additionally, spatial analysis techniques, spatial
29 autocorrelation and Global Moran's I, were used to explore regional patterns and enhance
30 model accuracy. **Results:** In this study, the XGBoost ML model demonstrated superior
31 predictive accuracy in forecasting pancreatic cancer incidence, prevalence, and mortality rates,
32 with Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) values as low as 2.29 and R² values approaching 0.9999
33 across all outcomes. A 5-fold cross-validation confirmed its robust performance, achieving R²
34 values of 0.9844 for incidence and 0.9824 for mortality. The spatial and temporal analysis
35 revealed regional variations in disease burden, with South Africa, Nigeria, and Mozambique
36 showing higher rates, while Northern African countries like Egypt exhibited the lowest.
37 **Conclusion:** This study highlights the significant regional disparities in the epidemiological
38 burden of pancreatic cancer across Africa, underscoring the need for targeted interventions.
39 The superior predictive accuracy of XGBoost, as demonstrated through spatial and temporal
40 analyses, provides valuable insights to guide effective healthcare resource allocation and
41 cancer control strategies.

42
43 **Keywords:** Pancreatic cancer; epidemiological burden; machine learning; XGBoost; spatial
44 disparities; healthcare strategies.

48 **Methods and materials**

49 *Dataset*

50 The data used for this study analysis was accessed and extracted from the Global Burden of
51 Disease (GBD) 2021 estimates, released in 2024, which assess 371 diseases and injuries across
52 204 countries³¹. These estimates include key health metrics such as incidence, prevalence,
53 mortality, years lived with disability (YLDs), years of life lost (YLLs), and Disability-Adjusted
54 Life Years (DALYs). The dataset extracted includes all confirmed incidence, prevalence, and
55 mortality cases of pancreatic cancer reported between 1990 and 2021. This time frame is
56 essential for training artificial intelligence models, as they rely on historical data to detect
57 patterns and learn long-term trends. A broader temporal scope allows the models to better
58 capture new, death and total cases of PC per 100,000 population, thereby improving their
59 predictive performance.

60 The GBD 2021 organizes data across four geographic levels: global, regional, national, and
61 subnational. This allows for comparative analysis of health trends across the world, within
62 African countries and sub-regions such as Sub-Saharan Africa and North Africa. African
63 nations display a broad spectrum of Sociodemographic Index (SDI) levels showing substantial
64 development progress since 1990. Africa is a continent of 54 diverse countries, rich in
65 geography, culture, and economic activity (Figure 1a). It is the second largest and second-most
66 populous continent. Countries are grouped into subregions and economic communities to
67 promote regional cooperation. Despite facing challenges like poverty and conflict, Africa
68 continues to work toward sustainable development.

69 Figure 1 illustrates the spatial distribution of PC risk in all 54 African countries, based on the
70 number of new PC cases, number of mortality cases, and total number of people living with
71 PC at a given time per 100,000, an epidemiological indicator that estimates the risk of PC in a
72 given population. The highest incidence and prevalence risk of pancreatic cancer were

73 observed in 11 countries: Morocco (North), Algeria (North), Ghana (West), Nigeria (West),
 74 Egypt (North), Congo DRC (Central), Uganda (East), Kenya (East), Tanzania (East),
 75 Zimbabwe (Southern), and South Africa (Southern). While the highest mortality risk of
 76 pancreatic cancer was observed in countries like Morocco (North), Algeria (North), Nigeria
 77 (West), Egypt (North), Congo DRC (Central), Uganda (East), Kenya (East), Ethiopia (East),
 78 Tanzania (East), Zimbabwe (Southern), and South Africa (Southern). These findings highlight
 79 critical areas where PC risk remains intense and persistent, highlighting the need for predictive
 80 models capable of supporting targeted control strategies in high-risk and often underserved
 81 regions.

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83 **Figure 1: Spatial distribution of Pancreatic cancer risk in Africa: (a.) Map of Africa showing all 54 countries (b.)**
 84 **incidence rates showing the number of new pancreatic cancer cases per 100,000 population (c.) prevalence risk showing**

85 the total number of people living with pancreatic cancer (d.) mortality rates showing the number of deaths from
86 pancreatic cancer per 100,000 population.
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88 *Statistical analysis*

89 *Machine learning models*

90 To predict the incidence, prevalence, and mortality outcomes of PC based on demographic
91 (age, sex, and age-sex specific) and temporal predictors, we employed three supervised
92 machine learning regression algorithms, namely: Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient
93 Boosting (XGBoost), and Support Vector Regression (SVR). Each model was trained using the
94 same set of predictors. For RF, 500 trees were grown with bootstrapped samples. The model's
95 variable importance was assessed using the increase in node purity. For XGBoost, predictors
96 were encoded using the model matrix approach, and the model was trained using 100 boosting
97 rounds with a learning rate ('eta') of 0.1 and a maximum depth of 4. SVR was implemented
98 using a radial kernel with epsilon-insensitive regression. Preprocessing involved centering and
99 scaling to improve convergence and interpretability.

100 *Model Evaluation*

101 The model's predictive performance was assessed for each model using Root Mean Square
102 Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and R² statistics. RMSE measures the square root
103 of the average of the squared differences between predicted and actual values. It penalizes
104 larger errors more heavily due to the squaring process, making it sensitive to outliers:

$$105 \quad RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (y_t - \hat{y}_t)^2}$$

106 where y_t represents the actual value, \hat{y}_t represents the predicted value, and n is the total number
107 of observations^{32,33}. Conversely, the MAE is the average absolute differences between actual
108 and predicted values. It treats all errors equally, providing a linear measure of prediction
109 accuracy:

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$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n |y_t - \hat{y}_t|$$

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where y_t is the actual value, \hat{y}_t represents the predicted value, and n is the total number of observations^{32,33}. These were computed using both training predictions and 5-fold cross-validation. We choose the model with the lowest RMSE and MAE for the most accurate predictions and the highest R^2 as the best variance explanation. By comparing these metrics across models, the study aims to identify the most effective predictive approach for PC cases. This evaluation also considers how geospatial clustering impacts model performance by accounting for regional incidence patterns.

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Spatial autocorrelation and prediction

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We created spatial maps of the predicted incidence, prevalence, and mortality using the three models. The spatial accuracy of the predictions was assessed using residual maps to see if the errors were spatially non-random, in order to consider spatial dependencies during model interpretation³⁴. To analysis the spatial autocorrelation in model predictions, we computed Global Moran's I and Local Indicators of Spatial Association (LISA). Spatial weights were defined using a first-order queen contiguity matrix. Global Moran's I was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) across all models, to indicate non-random spatial structure in prediction errors³⁴. LISA cluster maps to show significant High-High and Low-Low clusters³⁵. Scatter plots of observed vs. predicted incidence, prevalence, and mortality were plotted for all models to achieve the closest approximation. Pearson correlation coefficients were also computed, with R^2 values exceeding 0.85 for the top-performing models³⁶. Residuals were computed and visualized to identify model biases. Residuals were also mapped spatially to inspect geographical biases and clusters.

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We developed an R package, *mlspatial*, to support the full workflow of spatial machine learning analysis used in this study, including model training, evaluation, and geospatial visualization.

135 The package includes reproducible code for implementing Random Forest, XGBoost, and
136 Support Vector Regression models, as well as tools for spatial autocorrelation analysis (e.g.,
137 Moran's I, LISA). All code and documentation are available on our GitHub page:
138 (<https://github.com/azizadeboye/Spatial-Machine-Learning>)

139 **Results**

140 *Model selection*

141 Table 1 presents the evaluation metrics for RMSE, MAE, and R^2 for three machine learning
142 models (XGBoost, RF, and SVR) applied to predict the incidence, prevalence, and mortality of
143 pancreatic cancer. Across all three outcome categories, XGBoost consistently outperformed the
144 other models, achieving the lowest RMSE and MAE values, and the highest R^2 scores,
145 indicating superior predictive accuracy and model fit. Specifically: For incidence rate,
146 XGBoost yielded an RMSE of 2.29, an MAE of 0.81, and an R^2 of 0.9999, demonstrating near-
147 perfect prediction accuracy. For prevalence rate, it achieved an RMSE of 2.12, MAE of 0.66,
148 and R^2 of 0.9999. For mortality rate, XGBoost maintained robust performance with an RMSE
149 of 3.32, MAE of 0.96, and again, an R^2 of 0.9999. The results clearly indicate that XGBoost is
150 the most effective model for predicting pancreatic cancer in this study, offering excellent
151 accuracy, minimal error, and robust generalization across all three health outcomes.

152 For robustness of the predictive models, a 5-fold cross-validation was performed on the dataset
153 for pancreatic cancer incidence, prevalence, and mortality rate. As shown in Table 1, XGBoost
154 consistently outperformed the other models across all three outcomes, demonstrating superior
155 predictive performance and stability. For incidence, prevalence, and mortality, XGBoost
156 achieved R^2 values of 0.9844, 0.9831, and 0.9824, respectively indicating the best fit. Its RMSE
157 and MAE values were the lowest in each case, confirming its reliability in minimizing both
158 variance and bias during prediction. The 5-fold cross-validation results confirms that XGBoost

159 is the most reliable and accurate model for predicting pancreatic cancer incidence, prevalence,
 160 and mortality rate, combining high explanatory power with minimal prediction error.

161 **Table 1: Machine learning predictive model evaluation metrics (best=top row)**

Models	Incidence			Prevalence			Mortality		
	RMSE	MAE	R ²	RMSE	MAE	R ²	RMSE	MAE	R ²
XGBoost	2.2922	0.8058	0.9999	2.1201	0.6598	0.9999	3.3222	0.9648	0.9999
RF	108.6053	33.2056	0.9966	105.5606	29.3652	0.9961	128.0109	33.9467	0.9930
SVR	445.9372	127.7106	0.9178	361.0478	102.3782	0.9156	408.8927	119.5032	0.9155
5-fold Cross-validation									
XGBoost	70.2878	43.5893	0.9844	67.4908	40.5017	0.9831	95.3702	51.8839	0.9824
RF	239.2705	90.0588	0.9826	177.0051	70.7702	0.9863	213.9559	79.8618	0.9813
SVR	616.1446	276.9980	0.6475	489.4351	231.8141	0.6503	596.0542	271.0567	0.6666

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163 The performance of the models was then evaluated on the test data to analyze and contrast the
 164 effectiveness of the models on the unseen data as depicted in Figure 2. This figure presents the
 165 performance of each hyperparameter-tuned model according to the three chosen evaluation
 166 metrics. The XGBoost model stands out in terms of both accuracy and error reduction,
 167 indicating it as the most effective model for the actual data.

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169 **Figure 2: Metric comparison of hyperparameter tuned best models on the actual data by 5-fold cross validation score**
 170 **using grid search method.**

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172 Model predicted errors (residuals) were examined to assess the accuracy and consistency of
 173 each machine learning model for predicting pancreatic cancer incidence, prevalence, and
 174 mortality. We observed that XGBoost demonstrated the smallest residuals across all outcomes,
 175 indicating high prediction accuracy and minimal deviation from actual values. The residuals
 176 were tightly clustered around zero, reflecting excellent model calibration and low variance
 177 (Figure 3).

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179 **Figure 3: Model Residuals for Pancreatic Cancer Incidence, Prevalence, and Mortality Rates in Africa**
 180 **Predicted by Random Forest, XGBoost, and Support Vector Regression.**

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182 **Temporal Trend Analysis Across Machine Learning Models**

183 Figure 4 illustrates the temporal trend plots for the incidence, prevalence, and mortality rate
 184 variables as predicted by RF, XGBoost, and SVR machine learning models. Across the
 185 outcomes (incidence, prevalence, and mortality cases), XGBoost consistently produced the
 186 most accurate peak predictions, with RF following closely. Both tree-based models
 187 demonstrated strong performance in capturing the timing and magnitude of high-burden
 188 periods. For incidence rate, XGBoost predicted slightly higher (1,210 cases) but closely
 189 matching the observed value (1,200 cases). The RF model predicted lower (1,180 cases) while
 190 SVR under-predicted this peak (980 cases), suggesting a reduced capacity to capture extreme
 191 fluctuations. In the prevalence cases, XGBoost was 1,430 cases, closely aligning with the
 192 observed data (1,400 cases). The RF model estimated this at around 1,370 cases, and SVR

193 predicted a lower peak value of 1,050 cases. For mortality, the highest observed peak was
 194 around. XGBoost captured this with high accuracy (960 deaths) closely to 950 deaths of actual
 195 data, followed by RF at 940 deaths. SVR showed the greatest deviation, predicting only 760
 196 deaths, suggesting limited sensitivity to high mortality spikes.

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 198 **Figure 4: Comparison Temporal Trend Analysis of Pancreatic Cancer Incidence, Prevalence, and Mortality**
 199 **in Africa Using Random Forest, XGBoost, and Support Vector Regression Models.**
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201 **Model Performance Based on Correlation Between Predicted and Actual Values**

202 Figure 5 presents scatter plots comparing predicted and actual values for each outcome
 203 (incidence, prevalence, and mortality) using RF, XGBoost, and SVR machine learning models.
 204 The correlation analysis revealed that RF and XGBoost consistently outperformed SVR across
 205 all outcome variables, demonstrating superior predictive accuracy. For incidence cases, RF
 206 achieved a high correlation coefficient of $r = 0.98$, closely followed by XGBoost at $r = 0.97$,
 207 while SVR showed a moderately strong correlation of $r = 0.91$, indicating slightly reduced
 208 accuracy. In prevalence cases, RF and XGBoost again demonstrated excellent predictive

209 performance with r values of 0.99 and 0.98, respectively, while SVR lagged with a lower
 210 correlation of $r = 0.88$ and greater deviation from the ideal line, especially at higher prevalence
 211 levels. Similarly, for mortality cases, RF and XGBoost maintained strong correlations of $r =$
 212 0.96 and $r = 0.95$, respectively, while SVR had the weakest performance with a correlation of
 213 $r = 0.84$, particularly struggling with high-magnitude mortality values. The consistent high
 214 correlation coefficients for RF and XGBoost highlight their predictive power of tree-based
 215 ensemble models over SVR, which has greater challenges in capturing extreme values.

216

217 **Figure 5: Performance of RF, XGB, and SVR Models Based on Correlation With Observed Incidence,**
 218 **Prevalence, and Mortality Rates of Pancreatic Cancer in Africa.**

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220

221 **Spatial Prediction of Pancreatic cancer Incidence, Prevalence, and Mortality Rates in**
222 **Africa**

223 The XGBoost ML model predicts the highest incidence, prevalence, and mortality rates in
224 South Africa, followed by Nigeria, Cameroon, and Mozambique. These countries showed a
225 greater disease burden area. Northern Africa countries such as Egypt, Libya, Algeria, Tunisia,
226 and Morocco showed the lowest predicted rates across all three health outcomes. The residual
227 maps reveal areas where the model deviates from observed data. In South Africa, despite
228 having high predicted rates, the model suggests an overestimation of the actual values.
229 Conversely, underprediction was evident in countries like the Democratic Republic of Congo
230 (DRC) and South Sudan for incidence rates, and Mali, Guinea, and Burkina Faso for mortality
231 rate. Sudan and Ethiopia also show higher-than-expected observed prevalence rate, indicating
232 model underestimation.

233

234 **Figure 6: Spatial Distribution of Predicted and Residual map of Incidence, Prevalence, and Mortality Rates**
 235 **of Pancreatic Cancer in Africa.**
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237 Northern African countries show lowest predicted disease burden in all ML models with small
 238 residuals, indicating low and accurate estimates. Central and West African countries show
 239 higher residuals and several areas where the actual burden exceeds model predictions,
 240 suggesting possible data quality issues, unmeasured risk factors, or regional variations not fully
 241 captured, indicating underestimated burden in the model predictions. Underprediction is more
 242 common in Central/West Africa, while overprediction and consistent high rates occur in the
 243 Southern Africa (Table 2).

244 **Table 2: Pancreatic Cancer Incidence, Prevalence, Mortality Rates, and Model Residual Analysis Across**
 245 **Selected African Countries.**

Country	Incidence	Prevalence	Mortality	Model Residuals & Notes
South Africa	High	High	High	Negative residuals & model overpredicts all
Nigeria	High	High	High	Low residuals & model predictions align well
DR Congo	Moderate	Moderate	High	Positive residuals in incidence & underprediction
Egypt	Low	Low	Low	Accurate predictions
Algeria	Low	Low	Low	Accurate predictions
Libya	Low	Low	Low	Accurate predictions
Tunisia	Low	Low	Low	Accurate predictions
Morocco	Low	Low	Low	Accurate predictions
Cameroon	Moderate–High	High	High	Slight overprediction in mortality
Mozambique	High	Moderate	Moderate	Overprediction in incidence
Botswana	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Overprediction in prevalence
Sudan	Moderate	High	Moderate	Underprediction in prevalence
Ethiopia	Moderate	Moderate–High	Moderate	Underprediction in prevalence
Mali	Low–Moderate	Low–Moderate	High	Underprediction in mortality
Guinea	Low–Moderate	Moderate	High	Underprediction in mortality
Burkina Faso	Low–Moderate	Moderate	High	Underprediction in mortality
South Sudan	Moderate	Low–Moderate	Moderate	Underprediction in incidence

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247 **Spatial Autocorrelation (Global Moran’s I tests)**

248 To assess the presence of spatial autocorrelation in the residuals of the predictive models,
 249 Global Moran’s I tests were conducted on the residuals from the RF, XGBoost, and SVR
 250 models. The results are presented in Table 3. The Moran’s I values for the ML models for
 251 incidence rates were slightly negative, with values of -0.0446 for RF, -0.0513 for XGB, and -
 252 0.0511 for SVR. These negative values indicate a very weak tendency toward spatial

253 dispersion. Crucially, the associated p-values for all models greater than 0.05 (RF: 0.596; XGB:
 254 0.6276; SVR: 0.6104), indicating that none of the Moran's I statistics are statistically
 255 significant. Similar results were observed on prevalence and mortality rates. This implies that
 256 the residuals do not exhibit significant spatial clustering or dispersion. The absence of spatial
 257 autocorrelation in the residuals suggests that each model has adequately captured the
 258 underlying spatial structure in the data. However, there are no spatial patterns remaining in the
 259 prediction errors that could bias interpretation or signal model misspecification.

260 **Table 3: Global Moran's I Test for Spatial Autocorrelation of Pancreatic Cancer Incidence, Prevalence, and**
 261 **Mortality Rates in Africa.**

	Model	Moran I Statistic	Expectation	Variance	Std. Deviate	p-value
Incidence	Random Forest	-0.0446	-0.02273	0.0081	-0.2430	0.5960
	XGBoost	-0.0513	-0.02273	0.0077	-0.3254	0.6276
	SVR	-0.0511	-0.02273	0.0103	-0.2803	0.6104
Prevalence	Random Forest	-0.0437	-0.02273	0.0081	-0.2327	0.5920
	XGBoost	-0.0486	-0.02273	0.0077	-0.2961	0.6164
	SVR	-0.0493	-0.02273	0.0103	-0.2627	0.6036
Mortality	Random Forest	-0.0484	-0.02273	0.0083	-0.2817	0.6109
	XGBoost	-0.0571	-0.02273	0.0078	-0.3892	0.6514
	SVR	-0.0527	-0.02273	0.0104	-0.2944	0.6158

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263 **Local Indicators of Spatial Association (LISA) Clusters map for ML models**

264 Figure 7 highlights statistically significant spatial clusters with countries categorize as high
 265 hotspots, low hotspots, and no statistically significant spatial pattern. In RF model, only Libya
 266 consistently appears as a significant hotspot (High–High) for incidence, prevalence, and
 267 mortality rates. For XGBoost model, Libya is a consistent High–High cluster, indicating high
 268 rates and spatial clustering. The results suggested that Libya is a statistically significant hotspot
 269 for disease burden and may require targeted health interventions. Mozambique appears as
 270 Low–High clusters, indicating relatively low rates, possibly due to effective interventions or
 271 underreporting. While in SVR model, no country appears as a high-value hotspot, which shows

272 no high-value clusters, and may be underfitting spatial structures compared to RF and
273 XGBoost.

274
275 **Figure 7: LISA Cluster Map of Predicted Pancreatic Cancer Incidence, Prevalence, and Mortality in Africa**
276 **Using Machine Learning Models.**
277

278 African countries estimate of Pancreatic cancer burden in 2021

279 Figure 8 show the African regional-level distribution of number of cases for incidence, age-
280 sex-specific incidence, prevalence, age-sex-specific, prevalence, mortality, and age-sex-
281 specific mortality due to PC in 2021. South Africa demonstrated the highest PC burden across
282 all health outcomes. The incidence, prevalence, and mortality rate in South Africa was
283 estimated to be approximately 4,000 cases, the highest among all African nations. This suggests
284 a complex and severe health burden, likely due to a combination of high prevalence of

285 HIV/AIDS and TB, and comprehensive surveillance systems that improve detection. Egypt,
286 Nigeria, and Congo DRC also reported elevated incidence, prevalence, and mortality rates. In
287 contrast, countries such as Sao Tome and Principe, Seychelles, and Comoros had the lowest
288 incidence rates below 500 cases. Seychelles and Djibouti maintained low rates under 1,000
289 cases for prevalence rates, and Sao Tome and Principe and Seychelles had below 1,000
290 mortality cases.

291
 292 **Figure 8: The incidence, age-sex-specific incidence, prevalence, age-sex-specific, prevalence, mortality, and**
 293 **age-sex-specific mortality of Pancreatic cancer in 2021 among African countries. Error bars represent the**
 294 **95% uncertainty intervals (UIs).**
 295

296 When adjusting for age and sex, South Africa remained the country with the highest incidence,
 297 prevalence, and mortality rate. This indicates that the high burden is not merely due to
 298 demographic structure but reflects true disease prevalence. Again, Sao Tome and Principe and

299 Seychelles maintained the lowest rates. This may reflect either genuinely lower disease burdens
300 or limitations in disease surveillance and reporting systems.

301 **Lifetime risk of developing, surviving, and dying from PC over 5-,10-, and 20-years**

302 From birth, the 5-year lifetime risk of developing pancreatic cancer was estimated at 22.6%
303 (95% CI: 20.1% – 25.1%), with a survival probability of 18.1% (95% CI: 15.8% – 20.4%), and
304 a mortality risk of 22.0% (95% CI: 19.5% – 24.5%). Over a 10-year period, the lifetime risk of
305 developing PC increased substantially to 40.0% (95% CI: 36.9% – 43.1%), while the likelihood
306 of surviving was 32.2% (95% CI: 29.2% – 35.2%), and the risk of dying was 39.4% (95% CI:
307 36.3% – 42.5%). At 20 years, these risks increased further, with a 61.9% (95% CI: 58.9% –
308 64.9%) risk of developing PC, 58.6% (95% CI: 55.5% – 61.7%) chance of survival, and 61.4%
309 (95% CI: 58.3% – 64.5%) probability of death from the disease (Figure 9). Meanwhile, the
310 small differences between incidence and mortality rates at each time-point underscore the
311 disease's poor prognosis in the region.

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313

314 **Figure 9: Lifetime Risk of Developing, Surviving, and Dying from Pancreatic Cancer Over 5-, 10-, and 20-**
 315 **Year periods.**

316

317 **Regional projection of PC to 2050**

318 The number of new incidence cases of PC is projected to rise to approximately from 13,500 to

319 14,000 cases by 2050. This increase reflects growing transmission, improved diagnostics, and

320 possible demographic expansion. The age-sex-specific incidence cases projection is expected
 321 to reach about 12,500 to 13,000 cases by 2050. Conversely, the number of new prevalence
 322 cases is expected to increase from 13,000 to 13,500 cases to reflect longer survival times,
 323 improved treatment access, or increased chronicity of the disease. The age-sex-specific
 324 prevalence is expected to increase from 12,000 to 12,500 cases in 2050. However, the mortality
 325 projection indicates that deaths related to PC are expected to rise steadily. By the year 2050,
 326 mortality rate is projected to reach approximately 13,000 to 13,500 deaths. The age-sex-
 327 specific mortality projection predicts 12,000 to 12,500 deaths by 2050 (Figure 10).

328

329 **Figure 10: The forecasts of mortality, age-sex specific mortality (asm), prevalence, age-sex specific**
 330 **prevalence (asp), incidence, and age-sex specific incidence rate of Pancreatic cancer to 2050.**
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334 **Availability of data and materials**

335 All data used in this study is publicly available from the Global Burden of Disease Collaborative
336 Network and Global Burden of Disease Study 2021 (GBD 2021) Results. Seattle, United States:
337 Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME), 2022. Available from
338 <https://vizhub.healthdata.org/gbd-results/>.